

Brushless DC Motor Speed Control using Conventional and Optimization Methods

Ravi Swetha¹, N. Leena², Smitha B.³, Vidhya M.P⁴

^{1,2,3,4}Electrical and Electronics Engineering Department, NSS College of Engineering,
Palakkad 678008, Kerala, India

ABSTRACT

This paper discuss the speed control of Brush less DC motor. PID controller has proved to be the best contrller in market available today. However, the main problem with a conventional PID controller is that it operates well and give the required control only over a particular operating condition. Any variation from this desired operating condition may alter the performance of PID controller. So in order to stabilize the operating characteristics an optimally tuned PID controller is developed and used here. The paper mainly deals with comparative analysis of different PID tuning techniques for speed control of BLDC motor and further selecting the best method for optimal speed control. The methods chosen for comparison are Z-N method, Basilio's method, GA and PSO method. Simulation results for the same are obtained with MATLAB simulink software.

Keywords: Genetic Algorithm (GA), Proportional- Integral- Derivative (PID), Particle Swarm Optimization (PSO), Ziegler Nichols (Z-N)

1. INTRODUCTION

Brushless DC motors are gaining its popularity over many other motors due to its added advantages like simplicity in construction, higher efficiency, better cooling, low maintenance cost, high reliability and lack of mechanical commutators and brushes. It provides trapezoidal emf waveform [1]. It is widely used in applications from fans, textile industry, automotives, and instrumentation, medical to aerospace applications. The speed of BLDC motor can be controlled with the help of sensors and by using sensor less control or back-emf method. Here speed control, achieved by using hall sensors and PID controller is discussed. Different PID tuning techniques were studied and performance analysis has been carried out by measuring and observing the step responses.

In most of the industrial applications the control is provided using PID controller [2]. The reason for this is, the three elements P,I and D can be used to reduce the system rise time, steady state error and settling time and overshoot. Thus it operates better than P and PI controllers. The performance of PID controller depends on the values selected for PID parameters K_p, K_i, K_d. The values can be selected by different methods [3]. It can be mathematically derived or can be selected using MATLAB tuning software with the aid of optimization tools. Different approaches where used for finding the values for PID parameters. The aim of all these methods is to improve the transient and steady state response of the plant. Conventional PID tuning methods are inefficient due to their variation in performance with change in temperature and load [4]. Methods like Ziegler-Nichols and Basilio's method were used to tune PID parameters but their transient and steady state responses were dissatisfactory. This led to the growth of optimal control strategies. Genetic Algorithm, Particle Swarm Optimization, Bee Foraging, and Ant Colony Optimization are some of the methods. Almost all the optimization techniques are better and equally efficient in tuning PID controllers. Here for the purpose of comparison and evaluating the best methods, GA and PSO are considered.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Transfer Function Model of BLDC Motor

Mathematical modeling of BLDC motor is done by deriving the transfer function model [5]. For symmetrical winding and balanced system voltage equation across the motor winding is given by equations (1)-(4),

$$V_a = R_a i_a + L_a \frac{di_a}{dt} + k_b \omega_m \quad (1)$$

$$V_b = R_b i_b + L_b \frac{di_b}{dt} + k_b \omega_m \quad (2)$$

$$V_c = R_c i_c + L_c \frac{di_c}{dt} + k_b \omega_m \quad (3)$$

$$T_e = k_t i_a = J \frac{d\omega_m}{dt} + B \omega_m + T_i \quad (4)$$

In these above equations R_a, R_b and R_c are the values of resistance in each phase. L_a, L_b and L_c are values of self-inductance in phase a, b and c. ω_m is the rotor speed. V_a, V_b, V_c is the per phase values of voltage and i = i_a = i_b = i_c are the phase

current of phase a, b and c respectively, T_e and T_l are electromagnetic torque developed by the motor and the load torque. J and B are inertia and friction coefficients [6].

Followed by these equations and carrying required substitutions the transfer function model is given as equation (5) and is derived for carrying out open loop analysis and closed loop analysis.

$$\frac{\omega(s)}{V(s)} = \frac{k_t}{L_a J s^2 + R J s + k_e k_t} \quad (5)$$

For closed loop study, PID controllers are cascaded with to check the performance with closed loop. The simulation results showed that transient and steady state properties are better for closed loop when compared to open loop step response [7].

2.2 PID Controller

The PID controller consists of three main parts: proportional, derivative and integral terms. The proportional term gives the reaction to the current error, derivative term determines the reaction to the rate of change of error and integral term determines the reaction to the sum of the errors for a definite time interval. The normalized equation of a proportional-integral-derivative (PID) controller is given in equation (6),

$$u(t) = K(e(t) + \frac{1}{T_i} \int_0^t e(t) dt + T_d \frac{de(t)}{dt}) \quad (6)$$

where K is called proportional constant, T_i , T_d , and $e(t)$ is the integral time, derivative time and the error; i.e., $e(t) = r(t) - y(t)$ where $r(t)$ is the reference input and $y(t)$ is the output. The equivalent transfer function in the s -domain is given by equation (7) and (8),

$$\frac{U(s)}{E(s)} = K \left[1 + \frac{1}{T_i s} + T_d (s) \right] \quad (7)$$

$$\frac{U(s)}{E(s)} = \left[K_p + \frac{K_i}{s} + K_d s \right] \quad (8)$$

The PID controller has less value for maximum overshoot and has no steady state error, due to the integral action. The process determines the values of K_p , K_i and K_d to achieve high performance, is known as controller tuning.

2.3 Conventional Methods of PID Tuning

Ziegler-Nichols method is a heuristic PID tuning tool. The main goal is to achieve better regulations including disturbance rejection. The main steps include,

- Define the model of plant transfer function
- Plot step response characteristics
- Calculate the deflection point
- Draw the tangent along the open loop response

Following all the above steps and taking required measurement the step response characteristics are calculated using Ziegler-Nichols tuning method. The values for K_p , K_i , K_d obtained for the plant model are 0.0453, 0.0017, 0.00359 respectively for the selected motor parameters. The results proved that Ziegler-Nichols method is not efficient to control the transient and steady state response of second order system. Another conventional method of PID tuning include Basilio's method in which Basilio developed a mathematical strategy for tuning PI and PID controllers. The method is done mainly to improve the transient response characteristics. This method is similar to that of Z-N method in which it solely relies upon the transfer function model and step response of plant [8]. The values for K_p , K_i , K_d obtained for the plant model are 0.189, 94.97, 4.3e-4 respectively for the given motor parameters. The results obtained using Basilio's method proved to be better than Z-N method and can be understood from the comparison table shown below.

2.4 Optimal PID Tuning Methods

Optimal PID is defined using PSO and GA method.

2.4.1 PSO METHOD

Particle Swarm Optimization is an optimization technique, which is population based. It relies upon the social behavior of bird flocking or fish schooling. The system is started with a population of random solutions (initialization) and searches for optimal solution by updating each generations. In case of PSO method the major step taken towards finding optimal PID parameters are [9];

Figure 1: BLDC motor simulink model

Table 1: Parameter comparison 1

Parameter	Open Loop	Closed Loop Without PID	Closed Loop With PID
Overshoot	24.3%	0%	0%
Rise Time t_r	0.00321 s	0.017 s	0.00057 s
Settling Time t_s	0.0182 s	0.0271 s	0.00101 s

Figure 2: Open loop control of BLDC motor step response.

Figure 3: Closed loop control of BLDC motor with PID tuned using trial and error method

- Problem definition: Here the cost function in any variable say ‘x’ is defined which is to be minimized. Also, define Kp, Ki, Kd as a function of ‘x’ along with plant transfer function model.
 - Defining PSO parameters: Maximum number of iteration, total population size are defined here.
 - Initialization: Particle velocity, position, cost, global best are defined.
 - Executing the main loop: Main loop is a ‘For loop’ which begins from the first iteration to the last one. Here under the
 - For loop for each iteration carried out the values of Kp, Ki, Kd are updated with the best values.
 - Display: Iteration with best values are displayed.
- The values for Kp, Ki, Kd obtained for the plant model are 3.11, 6.98, 5.15 respectively for the given motor parameters. The step response obtained for the given PID parameters is shown in fig.4.

2.4.2 GENETIC ALGORITHM OPTIMIZATION

Genetic Algorithm (GA) is a search heuristic inspired by Charles Darwin’s theory of evolution. It mimics the natural selection process, where the fittest individuals are chosen for reproduction to generate offspring for future generations. The GA process involves five main phases;

Table 2. Comparison of parameters of ZN method and Basilio’s method

Parameter	ZN method	Basilio’s method
Overshoot	2.5%	0%
Rise time t_r	2.1 ms	2.7 ms
Settling time t_s	0.26s	5.1 ms

- Initial population
- Fitness function
- Selection
- Crossover
- Mutation

In case of GA optimization the major steps taken for finding optimal PID parameters are discussed as follows. Mention the fitness function in any variable say ‘x’. Define the plant relation and number of variables. Observe the limits for iteration to begin with and run the iteration code to generate the optimum parameters values [10]. The values for Kp, Ki, Kd obtained for the plant model are 6.917, 1.1948, 7.7097 respectively for the given motor parameters. The step response obtained for the given PID parameters are as shown in Fig, 5 and Fig.6.

Considering the performance indices the PID parameters are optimized. The objective functions are Mean of the Squared Error (MSE), Integral of the Squared Error (ISE) and Integral of Absolute Magnitude of the Error (IAE).

$$MSE = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^n e(t)^2 \qquad ISE = \int_0^T e^2(t)dt \tag{9} \tag{10}$$

$$ITAE = \int_0^T |e(t)|dt \tag{11}$$

The function of GA is to minimize the error signals, or to minimize the value of performance indices. Smaller the performance indices, fitter the chromosomes will be.

$$Fitness = \frac{1}{PerformanceIndex} \tag{12}$$

The fitness is calculated using Eqn. (12).

Table 3: Parameter Comparison

Parameter	GA Optimization	PSO
Overshoot	0%	0%
Rise time	0.40 ms	0.57 ms
Settling time	0.71ms	1.07 ms

3. RESULTS

From the simulation results it can be clearly seen that GA tuned PID controller exhibits better transient and steady state response for BLDC motor. GA tuned BLDC motor has least value for rise time, settling time and overshoot when compared with other conventional methods. The fig.7 and fig. 8 shows the phase voltage and reference speed tracking waveforms for GA tuned PID controlled BLDC motor

Table 4: Controller parameter from GA tuning

Controller parameters	Proportional gain(Kp)	Integral gain (Ki)	Derivative gain (Kd)
MSE	14.53	13.77	0.25
ISE	15.93	16.55	0.25
IAE	12	12.05	0.03

Table 5: Performance measure for different tuning methods

Performance Measures	Rise time tr (msec)	Settling time ts (msec)	Maximum Percentage Overshoot (%)
Controller tuning techniques			
Conventional (Z-N)	2.1	0.26	2.5
GA with MSE criterion	0.003	0.006	0
GA with ISE criterion	0.003	0.006	0
GA with IAE criterion	0.03	0.054	0

4 CONCLUSION

As BLDC motor is gaining its popularity in all aspects there is a need of attaining an optimum control over it. This paper depicts the work related to the optimal control of BLDC motor. The control mechanism demonstrated here have succeeded in improving the step response characteristics of BLDC motor providing a smooth control over its speed.

Table 6: BLDC motor specification

Number of phases	3
Number of poles (P)	4
Rated speed	4000 rpm
Rated current	5 A
Rated voltage	36 V
Per phase Resistance (R)	0.57 ohm
Inductance (L)	1.5 mH
Moment of inertia (J)	0.0000023 kg/m ²
Rated Torque (T)	0.42 Nm
Torque constant	0.082 Nm/A

Figure 4: BLDC step response with PSO tuned PID controller

Figure 5: BLDC step response with GA tuned PID controller

Figure 6: Step response comparison

Figure 7: Trapezoidal phase voltages of BLDC motor

Figure 8: Reference speed tracking of controller with variable motor load

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